

A LAYER WISE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PLATES AND SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a layer wise finite element formulation for static and dynamic analysis of composite plates and shells is presented. The triangular element developed is based on degenerated 3D elasticity theory and uses an assumed shear strain field. The thickness variables are eliminated using a substructuring technique. Examples of application of the proposed formulations are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Layer-wise theory for analysis of composite plates was introduced by Reddy^{1,2,3} to overcome the stress continuity limitations of single layer models. In layer wise theory the 3D displacement field is first expanded as a linear combination of the thickness coordinate as

$$u_i(x, y, z) = u_i^0(x, y) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} u_i^j(x, y)\Phi_j(z) \quad (1)$$

where n_i is the number of divisions across the thickness. The displacements $u_i^j(x, y)$ are now interpolated over each layer interface using a standard finite element approximation. The thickness interpolating functions Φ_j are piece-wise constant across the thickness direction. This implies that displacements are continuous across the thickness but the shear strains are discontinuous. This allows to obtain a continuous field of transverse shear strains at the layer interfaces.

In this paper a triangular element for the analysis of laminated plates and shells based on layer-wise theory is presented. The element can be considered as an extension of the linear/quadratic triangular Reissner-Mindlin plate element based on an assumed shear strain formulation presented by Zienkiewicz et al.⁴, Taylor and Papadopoulos⁵ Oñate et al.^{6,7,8}. The in-plane displacements are linearly interpolated within each layer and they are eliminated during the global assembly process using a substructuring technique. Details of the element formulation are given in next sections.

FORMULATION OF A TRIANGULAR PLATE ELEMENT BASED ON LAYER-WISE THEORY

The element geometry is shown in Figure 1. Note that the element has n_l layers and $n_l + 1$ layer interfaces. The horizontal (in-plane) displacement field within the k th layer is interpolated as

Figure 1. Triangular element based on layer-wise theory.

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \end{Bmatrix} &= \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(\xi, \eta) \left[N^k(\zeta) \begin{Bmatrix} u_i^k \\ v_i^k \end{Bmatrix} + N^{k+1}(\zeta) \begin{Bmatrix} u_i^{k+1} \\ v_i^{k+1} \end{Bmatrix} \right] + \\ &+ \sum_{i=4}^6 N_i(\xi, \eta) \mathbf{e}_{i-3} \left[N^k(\zeta) \Delta u_{t_i}^k + N^{k+1}(\zeta) \Delta u_{t_i}^{k+1} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta u_{t_i}^k (i = 4, 5, 6)$ are the mid-side incremental displacements in the direction of each side defined by unit vectors \mathbf{e}_{i-3} for the k th layer interface.

The vertical deflection is assumed a constant distribution across the thickness and it is interpolated over the plate mid surface as

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(\xi, \eta) w_i \quad (3)$$

In (2) and (3)

$$\begin{aligned} N_i(\xi, \eta) &= L_i \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ N_4(\xi, \eta) &= 4L_1L_2 \quad , \quad N_5(\xi, \eta) = 4L_2L_3 \quad , \quad N_6(\xi, \eta) = 4L_1L_3 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where L_i are the linear shape functions of the 3 node triangle⁹ and

$$N^k(\zeta) = \frac{1-\zeta}{2} \quad , \quad N^{k+1}(\zeta) = \frac{1+\zeta}{2} \quad (5)$$

Eqs.(2) and (3) imply a hierarchical quadratic interpolation for the horizontal displacements u and v over each interface whereas a linear interpolation for w is used. Note that for a single layer the element simplifies to the linear/quadratic triangle based on Reissner-Mindlin plate theory⁴⁻⁸.

It has been shown that the undesirable defect of "locking" in thick plate elements when used for thin plate analysis can be avoided by imposing "a priori" a shear strain field compatible with the discretized displacement field⁶⁻⁸. A discussion of the compatibility conditions to be satisfied by the displacement, rotations and shear strain fields can be found in⁴⁻⁹. Results presented in these references shown the good behaviour of a triangular thick plate element identical to that proposed here for a single layer with the assumed shear strain field shown

in Figure 1, i.e. the shear strain are assumed linear within the element, with constant values of the tangential shear strains along each side.

Eqs.(2)-(3) and the shear strain assumptions mentioned allow to express the generalized "bending" and "transverse shear" strains for each element layer as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_b = \mathbf{B}_b \mathbf{a}^{(k)} \quad \text{and} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s = \mathbf{B}_s \mathbf{a}^{(k)} \quad (6)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_b = \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \right]^T \quad ; \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s = \left[\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right]^T \quad (7)$$

Note that the thickness strain ε_z is not taken into account in accordance with the plane stress assumption ($\sigma_z = 0$) typical of plate theory. In (6) \mathbf{B}_b and \mathbf{B}_s are the bending and "substitute" shear strain matrices for the layer which expressions can be found in [10,12] and \mathbf{a}^k is the layer displacement vector given by

$$\mathbf{a}^{(k)} = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \mathbf{a}^k \\ \mathbf{a}^{k+1} \\ w_1 \\ w_2 \\ w_3 \end{array} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where the superindex k refers to variables in the layer interfaces. Thus

$$\mathbf{a}^k = [u_1^k, v_1^k, u_2^k, v_2^k, u_3^k, v_3^k, \Delta u_{t_4}^k, \Delta u_{t_5}^k, \Delta u_{t_6}^k]^T \quad (9)$$

The layer stiffness matrix is computed by

$$\mathbf{K}^{(e)} = \int \int_{A^{(e)}} \int_{h^k} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} dV \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{B} = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \mathbf{B}_b \\ \mathbf{B}_s \end{array} \right\}$ and \mathbf{D} is the standard constitutive matrix for orthotropic laminated plates¹⁻³.

The volume integral (10) involves integration over the layer thickness h^k and the area $A^{(e)}$ of each layer interface. The simplicity of the linear shape functions N^k allows to perform the thickness integration explicitly, whereas a 2×2 Gaussian quadrature must be used for the interface area integral.

ELIMINATION OF LAYER DEGREES OF FREEDOM

The assembly of the stiffness matrices of the different layers resembles the assembly of 1D bar elements (see Figure 2). This allows to eliminate the in-plane degrees of freedom, \mathbf{a}^k , of a layer after they have been assembled in the global stiffness matrix. From Figure 2 we deduce that after assembly of the stiffness equations of the first layer, the variables \mathbf{a}^1 can be eliminated as

$$\mathbf{a}^1 = [\mathbf{K}_{11}^{(1)}]^{-1} [\mathbf{f}^1 - \mathbf{K}_{12}^{(1)} \mathbf{a}^2 - \mathbf{K}_{13}^{(1)} \mathbf{a}_w] \quad (11)$$

If the stiffness equations of the second layer are now assembled the global equations can be written in terms of \mathbf{a}^2 , \mathbf{a}^3 and \mathbf{a}_w . Thus the variables of the second interface \mathbf{a}^2 can now be eliminated by an equation similar to (11). The procedure is repeated by subsequently assembling the equation of a new layer and eliminating the variables of the k th interface, \mathbf{a}^k , in terms of those of the $k+1$ interface, \mathbf{a}^{k+1} , and the vertical deflections \mathbf{a}_w .

This elimination technique yields a final systems of equations involving only the variables of the last (upper) interface \mathbf{a}^{n_i+1} and the vertical deflection variables \mathbf{a}_w i.e.

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc} \bar{\mathbf{K}}_{11} & \bar{\mathbf{K}}_{12} \\ \bar{\mathbf{K}}_{21} & \bar{\mathbf{K}}_{22} \end{array} \right] \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \mathbf{a}^{n_i+1} \\ \mathbf{a}_w \end{array} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \bar{\mathbf{f}}^{n_i+1} \\ \bar{\mathbf{f}}_w \end{array} \right\} \quad (12)$$

Figure 2. Structure of the global stiffness equations for a laminated plate with n_l layers.

where $(\bar{\cdot})$ means that the coefficients have been adequately modified by the elimination process. Solution of (12) allows to recover all the variables of the lower interfaces in terms of those of the upper ones and the vertical deflection variables \mathbf{a}_w via an equation similar to (11). This elimination technique was first suggested in the context of laminated plate analysis by Owen and Li,¹³⁻¹⁵ and subsequently used by the authors^{10-12,16}.

FREE VIBRATION ANALYSIS

The computation of the natural frequencies involves the solution of the standard eigenvalue problem

$$[\mathbf{K} - \lambda^2 \mathbf{M}] \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0} \quad (13)$$

Since the vibration modes have a strong vertical component and the vertical displacement is common for all the layers, the mass associated to this displacement is assumed to be concentrated in the last layer,

Eq.(13) can be solved by means of the substructuring technique explained in previous section^{12,13,16}. After appropriate condensation of all horizontal degrees of freedom for the different layers we have

$$[\hat{\mathbf{K}}_w - \lambda^2 \mathbf{M}_w] \mathbf{a}_w = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_w$ is the stiffness matrix of last layer associated to the vertical deflections, \mathbf{M}_w is the mass matrix concentrated in the last layer and \mathbf{a}_w contain the deflection variables only.

Eq.(14) can be solved using standard procedures (i.e. inverse iteration) to obtain the natural frequencies λ . The corresponding eigenvectors involving all degrees of freedom for the interfaces are obtained from the substructuring approach.

GEOMETRICALLY NON LINEAR BEHAVIOUR

Geometrically non linear effects can be easily taken into account. In this work von-Karman's assumption have been used in the framework of a total lagrangean approach. The resulting non linear system of equations has been solved using a Newton-Raphson solution procedure. The solution of the displacement increments for each iteration can be simplified by using the substructuring approach proposed earlier on the tangent matrix and the residual force vector so that only the nodal displacements of last layer are involved. Note however that the full residual force vector for all layers must be computed at each iteration to check convergence.

The computation of initial buckling loads follows standard procedures⁹ which involve the solution of an eigenvalue problem similar to (13). Here again the substructuring approach leads to a considerable reduction of computational effort.

EXTENSION TO SHELL ANALYSIS

The laminate plate element previously presented can be easily extended to shell analysis. A facet shell formulation has been used here^{9,11,16}. This simply implies computation of the element stiffness matrix in a local coordinate systems followed by an adequate transformation to the global system. The substructuring approach explained earlier can then be applied to the global equation system in a straight forward manner. Further details of this procedure can be found in^{11,12}.

EXAMPLES

Simple supported square composite plate

The first example studied is a simple supported square plate of high modulus graphite-epoxy. The geometry and material properties are shown in Figure 3. Five material layers are considered with orientations 0/90/0/90/0 and thicknesses $h/6 / h/4 / h/6 / h/4 / h/6$. Uniformly distributed sinusoidal loading is assumed with $q = q_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{a}$.

Table I shows some results for the central deflection and the stresses at some characteristic points obtained for different thickness ratios (a/h). The solution obtained by Stavsky¹⁷ using classical laminate plate theory (CLT) is also shown for comparison. Note the discrepancy of results for thick situations due to the effect of shear deformation, not taken into account in CLT.

Also it is worth mentioning the considerable reduction in the number of degrees of freedom of the equation system from a total number of 1984 dof (for a mesh of $n = 8$ elements per interface) to 384. This shows more evidently if the number of layers is further increased keeping the same discretization at interface level.

Vibration analysis of a simple square supported laminate plate

The plate has a width/thickness ratio of $a/h = 10$ and it has been analyzed for a sequence of stacks $90^\circ/90^\circ/\dots/0^\circ$ of equal thickness and the following material properties

$$\frac{G_{lt}}{E_t} = 0.5 \quad ; \quad \frac{G_{lh}}{E_t} = 0.2 \quad ; \quad \nu_{lt} = \nu_{lh} = 0.25 \quad , \quad l = 1.0$$

Different values of the ratio $\frac{E_l}{E_t}$ have been taken ($l =$ longitudinal, $t =$ transversal, $h =$ thickness directions). Regular meshes of $8 \times 8 \times m$ have been used. The number of analysis layers (m) has been taken equal to that of material layers.

Figure 3. Simple supported square laminated plate (5 layers of Graphite-Epoxy composites)
 a) Geometry and material properties. b) Thickness distribution of in-plane normal and shear stresses for $a/h = 4$.

MESH	a/h	w_c ($a/2, a/2$)	$\bar{\sigma}_x$ ($a/2, a/2, \pm h/2$)	$\bar{\sigma}_y$ ($a/2, a/2, \pm h/2$)	$\bar{\tau}_{xz}$ ($0, a/2, 0$)	$\bar{\tau}_{yz}$ ($a/2, 0, 0$)
$n = 2$	4	5.0097	$\pm .585$	$\pm .397$.160	.171
$n = 4$	4	5.6431	$\pm .625$	$\pm .455$.202	.212
$n = 8$	4	5.7582	$\pm .625$	$\pm .473$.21775	.226
CLT	4	4.291	$\pm .651$	$\pm .626$	N.A.	.233
$n = 2$	20	1.0226	$\pm .4575$	$\pm .340$.170	.151
$n = 4$	20	1.1624	$\pm .5225$	$\pm .373$.228	.191
$n = 8$	20	1.1946	$\pm .535$	$\pm .378$.250	.207
CLT	20	1.145	$\pm .539$	$\pm .380$.268	.212
$n = 2$	100	.8439	$\pm .468$	$\pm .318$.178	.148
$n = 4$	100	.971693	$\pm .528$	$\pm .396$.259	.186
$n = 8$	100	1.001176	$\pm .539$	$\pm .362$.272	.210
CLT	100	1.0	$\pm .539$	$\pm .359$.272	.205

Results are normalized using:

$$w_c = \frac{\pi^4 Q w}{12 s^4 h q_0} \quad (\bar{\sigma}_x, \bar{\sigma}_y) = \frac{1}{q_0 s^2} (\sigma_x, \sigma_y)$$

$$(\bar{\tau}_{xz}, \bar{\tau}_{yz}) = \frac{1}{q_0 s^2} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}), \quad s = a/h \quad Q = 4G_{lt} + [E_l + E_t(1 + 2\nu_{th})]/(1 - \nu_{lt}\nu_{th})$$

Table I. Central deflection and stresses for simple supported square plates of high modulus graphite-epoxy under distributed sinusoidal loading.

	N° layers	$\frac{E_l}{E_t} = 3$	$\frac{E_l}{E_t} = 10$	$\frac{E_l}{E_t} = 20$	$\frac{E_l}{E_t} = 30$	$\frac{E_l}{E_t} = 40$
<i>Noor</i> ¹⁷	2	0.25031	0.27938	0.30698	0.32705	0.34250
<i>CLT</i>	2	0.27082	0.30968	0.35422	0.39335	0.42884
<i>This work</i>	2	0.2623	0.29746	0.32758	0.34904	0.36550
<i>Noor</i> ¹⁷	4	0.26182	0.32578	0.37622	0.40660	0.42719
<i>CLT</i>	4	0.28676	0.38877	0.49907	0.58900	0.66690
<i>This work</i>	4	0.2688	0.3364	0.38787	0.41846	0.43904
<i>Noor</i> ¹⁷	6	0.26440	0.33657	0.39359	0.42783	0.45091
<i>CLT</i>	6	0.28966	0.40215	0.52234	0.61963	0.70359
<i>This work</i>	6	0.2702	0.3465	0.401163	0.43452	0.456819
<i>Noor</i> ¹⁷	10	0.26583	0.34350	0.40337	0.44011	0.46498
<i>CLT</i>	10	0.29115	0.40888	0.53397	0.63489	0.72184
<i>This work</i>	10	0.2795	0.3492	0.40875	0.44397	0.467593

Table II. Normalized natural frequencies in a simple supported square laminate plate.

Table II shows the normalized results for the first natural frequency normalized as $\hat{\lambda} = \frac{\lambda a^2}{h} / \frac{l}{E_t}$. Numerical results obtained coincide well those reported by Noor¹⁷ and also with those provided by CLT.

Stability analysis of simple supported square laminate plate

The same plate of previous example has been analyzed now for a symmetric stack sequence of $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/\dots/0^{\circ}$ of equal thickness with the following material properties

$$\frac{G_{lt}}{E_t} = 0.6 \quad ; \quad \frac{G_{lh}}{E_t} = 0.5 \quad ; \quad \nu_{lt} = \nu_{lh} = 0.25$$

A mesh of $4 \times 4 \times m$ elements has been used. Again the number of analysis layers (m) has been taken equal to that of material layers. The plate is assumed to be symmetrically compressed along two opposite edges.

Table III shows the normalized values of the critical axial force computed as $N_{cr} = \frac{\sigma_{cr} a^2}{E_t h^2}$ for different ratios of E_l/E_t . Results obtained by different authors for the same problem are also shown for comparison purposes^{13,17}. Note the divergence of results with those provided by classical Laminate theory (CLT) as the ratio E_l/E_t increases.

N° of layers		E_l/E_t				
		3	10	20	30	40
3	This work	5.2570	10.0860	15.6015	19.9915	23.5920
	Owen and Li ¹³	5.4026	9.9590	15.3201	19.6872	23.3330
	Noor ¹⁷	5.3044	9.7621	15.0191	19.3040	22.8807
	CLT	5.7538	11.4920	19.7120	27.9360	36.1600
5	This work	5.2545	10.2150	15.0890	20.9170	24.9695
	Owen and Li ¹³	5.4208	10.1609	15.9976	20.9518	25.2150
	Noor ¹⁷	5.3255	9.9603	15.6527	20.4663	24.5929
	CLT	5.7538	11.4920	19.7120	27.9360	36.1600
9	This work	5.2530	10.2800	16.3385	21.3980	25.9695
	Owen and Li ¹³	5.4187	10.1990	16.1560	21.2697	25.7093
	Noor ¹⁷	5.3352	10.0417	15.9153	20.9614	25.3436
	CLT	5.7538	11.4920	19.7120	27.9360	36.1600

Table III. Normalized values of critical axial force for a simple supported square laminated plate ($a/h = 10$).

Simple supported cylindrical laminate shell

The final example is the analysis of a laminate cylindrical shell simply supported across its boundary. The laminate is composed of three material layers of Graphite-Epoxy composites with orientations 90/0/90 with respect to the global axis y of Figure 4 where the geometrical and material properties are also shown.

Figure 4 Simple supported square laminated plate (3 layers of Graphite-Epoxy composites 90/0/90 with respect to axis y). Geometry and material properties ($\theta = 30^\circ$).

The analysis has been performed using three meshes of 4×4 , 6×6 and 8×8 elements. The thickness direction has been divided in 3, 6 and 24 layers for the 4×4 mesh and 24 analysis layers for the other two meshes. Table IV shows some of the numerical results obtained. Also the in-plane displacement across the thickness direction are given in Figure 5. Finally Figure 6 shows the stress σ_{yz} and σ_{xz} distribution across the thickness in two shell points: $x = a$, $y = 0.0$ and $x = 0.0$ $y = L$.

MESH	LAYERS	DISP X		$\theta = 30^\circ$ DISP Y		σ_{xx}		σ_{yy}		
		point	value	point	value	point	value	point	value	
4 x 4	3	MAX	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	0.257E-6	$(a, 0, h)$	0.325E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	6.86	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{h}{3})$	3.15
		MIN	$(0, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-0.457E-5	$(a, 0, 0)$	-0.282E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-7.67	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{2h}{3})$	-6.15
	6	MAX	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	0.334E-6	$(a, 0, h)$	0.337E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	9.18	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{h}{3})$	3.50
		MIN	$(0, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	-0.507E-5	$(a, 0, 0)$	-0.294E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-9.47	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{2h}{3})$	-6.56
	24	MAX	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	0.379E-6	$(a, 0, h)$	0.346E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	10.90	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{h}{3})$	3.90
		MIN	$(0, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	-0.525E-5	$(a, 0, 0)$	-0.303E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-10.60	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{2h}{3})$	-7.00
6 x 6	24	MAX	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	0.374E-6	$(a, 0, h)$	0.358E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	10.70	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{h}{3})$	3.94
		MIN	$(0, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	-0.535E-5	$(a, 0, 0)$	-0.312E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-10.30	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{2h}{3})$	-7.31
8 x 8	24	MAX	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	0.373E-6	$(a, 0, h)$	0.361E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	10.80	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{h}{3})$	4.00
		MIN	$(0, \frac{L}{2}, 0)$	-0.539E-5	$(a, 0, 0)$	-0.317E-5	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, h)$	-10.20	$(a, \frac{L}{2}, \frac{2h}{3})$	-7.34

Table IV. Some displacement and stress results for the example of Figure 5.

Figure 5 Comparison of in-plane displacement (in $x = 0, y = L$) across the thickness for different meshes and layer discretizations.

Figure 6 Thickness variation of stresses σ_{yz} and σ_{xz} .

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The triangular plate and shell elements proposed combine the advantages of the 2D layer-wise solid model with those of assumed shear strain models to deal with thin plate and shell situations. The thickness interpolation used allows to eliminate the thickness variables at assembly level, thus reducing considerably the computational effort. The examples presented shows the capability of the element for the analysis of laminate composite plates and shells. Current research on this topic by the authors includes the extension of the element formulation to account for material non linear effects.

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